

Exploring Staff Retention Factors at a State Research Institution (SRI) in Eastern Region, Ghana

Bandanaa Joseph^{*1}, Asiedu-Darko Emmanuel², Kotey Ashie Daniel³, Yankey Genevieve⁴

¹CSIR-Plant Genetic Resources Research Institute (PGRRI), P. O. Box 7, Bunso, Eastern Region, Ghana
ORCID: 0000-0001-9630-5308

²CSIR- Water Research Institute (WRI), P.O. Box M 32, Accra-Ghana
ORCID number: 0000-0001-5922-2298

³CSIR-Plant Genetic Resources Research Institute (PGRRI), P. O. Box 7, Bunso, Eastern Region, Ghana
ORCID number: 0000-0003-1816-2473

⁴Council for Scientific and Industrial Research - Head Office, Accra
ORCID number: 0009-0009-9150-5795

Article DOI: [10.55677/SSHRB/2025-3050-0605](https://doi.org/10.55677/SSHRB/2025-3050-0605)

DOI URL: <https://doi.org/10.55677/SSHRB/2025-3050-0605>

KEYWORDS: human resources; staff attrition; retention factors; state research institutions

ABSTRACT: The study investigates employee satisfaction and retention factors at a State Research Institute (SRIs) in Ghana. The research focuses on the dynamic nature of factors influencing employee satisfaction, covering 'motivational', 'primary hygiene', 'secondary hygiene', 'work environment', 'sense of belongingness', and 'growth and recognition' factors. Data was collected through quantitative and qualitative means i.e. structured questionnaire and Focus group Discussions. Through hypotheses testing and regression analysis, the study identifies significant influences on employee satisfaction within each category. The socio-demographic profile of staff is considered, revealing variations in satisfaction levels among different genders, roles, and work experiences. The study recommends targeted policies, including specialized training, work-life balance initiatives, and organizational culture enhancement. Recognizing and appreciating employee performance is emphasized to boost morale and satisfaction. Findings highlight the importance of a positive 'work environment', stress reduction programs, and recognition for good performance. Specific recommendations include reevaluating 'motivational' factors, strengthening mentoring programs, and enhancing leadership skills. The study recommends proactive measures, such as regular surveys, to stay aligned with evolving employee needs.

Corresponding Author:
Bandanaa Joseph

Published: June 17, 2025

License: This is an open access article under the CC BY 4.0 license:
<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

1. INTRODUCTION

Organizations worldwide grapple with the persistent challenge of employee turnover, a phenomenon that can significantly impact organizational productivity, financial performance, and overall sustainability (Allen et al., 2010). This challenge is particularly pronounced in developing countries like Ghana, where intense competition for talent and limited resources to attract and retain staff present additional hurdles (Ewool et al., 2021). State research institutions (SRIs) in Ghana are not immune to this trend, experiencing high employee turnover rates that result in reduced productivity and efficiency (Korantwi-Barimah, 2017). Previous studies have identified various factors influencing employee retention, including compensation, working conditions, recognition and reward systems, and career development opportunities (Mugo et al., 2018a; Shafiuddin, and Al Nassibi, 2022; Elsafty and Oraby, 2022). Therefore, a critical examination of staff retention factors at SRIs in Ghana is imperative for identifying underlying contributors to employee turnover and developing effective mitigation strategies.

The literature underscores that motivation, career development, remuneration, promotion, work-life balance, training and development, performance management, and job security are crucial indicators of organizational success (Al-Abbadi, 2021; Arokiasamy, 2013; Chukwuka, and Nwakoby, 2018). Although the precise factors motivating employees remain incompletely

understood, the significance of motivation and these indicators cannot be overstated (Jayasekara and Weerasinghe, 2018; Son and Kim, 2021). Research has consistently demonstrated that well-motivated employees tend to be more efficient and committed to organizational goals, making them more likely to remain with their institution (Rawashdeh and Tamimi, 2020; Tadesse, 2018). This is particularly crucial in low-income settings, where an institution's ability to fulfil its mandate relies on the motivation levels of its workforce (Arokiasamy, 2013). Therefore, the effective implementation of incentive packages is vital for safeguarding any institution's greatest asset—its staff (Rawashdeh and Tamimi, 2020).

In the context of a research institute, both financial and non-financial incentives are indispensable for motivating and retaining workers. These incentives significantly impact staff satisfaction, workplace performance, and, ultimately, research outcomes, thereby influencing the institution's visibility. Financial incentives, such as remuneration and promotion, along with non-financial incentives like work-life balance and training and development opportunities, play pivotal roles in staff retention, as evidenced by studies conducted by Mugo et al. (2018b), Shafiuddin, and Al Nassibi (2022), and Elsafty and Oraby (2022).

Research institutions are distinctive workplaces requiring specialized knowledge and expertise from their employees. Employee retention assumes heightened importance in these settings due to its direct impact on research outcomes and institutional visibility. Globally, numerous studies have been undertaken to identify employee retention factors in research institutions. For instance, a study by Mugo et al. (2018a) highlighted the critical roles of financial and non-financial incentives in staff retention in a Kenyan research institution. The study identified remuneration, promotion, work-life balance, training and development opportunities, and recognition and reward systems as pivotal factors influencing staff retention. Another study by Shakeel and But (2015) identified job security, 'work environment', and compensation as the most significant factors influencing employee retention in a research institution. Similarly, Saleem and Amin (2013) found that organizational support, 'work environment', and career development opportunities significantly influence employee retention in research institutions in Pakistan. Additionally, a study by Singh (2019) revealed that employee retention in research institutions is influenced by various factors, including compensation, job satisfaction, work-life balance, and recognition and reward systems. The study emphasized that non-financial incentives, such as training and development opportunities and flexible work arrangements, also contribute to staff retention in these institutions.

The findings of this study will provide valuable insights into the unique staff retention factors at SRIs in Ghana. These insights will inform the development of retention strategies aimed at reducing employee turnover and enhancing organizational productivity and sustainability. Furthermore, this research will contribute to the existing literature on staff retention, serving as a foundation for future studies in the field. The study seeks to address the following research questions:

- What are the most important retention factors that the SRI could use to retain core research staff?
- Does the socio-demographic profile of staff affect the tenure of employees?
- What factors do present and past employees consider as retention strategies?

2. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1. Study Area

The study was conducted in the Eastern region of Ghana, which is endowed with several State Research Institutions (SRIs) that have varied focuses, but predominantly, they are agro based.

2.2. Research Hypotheses

In relation to staff retention sub-factors, a set of 30 hypotheses was formulated and tested, with conclusions drawn based on the test results. These hypotheses were developed from previous studies by Deery (2008), Collins (2015), and Nabi et al. (2016). The factors influencing staff retention were categorized into six broad areas based on employees' perspectives toward retention. These categories include "motivational" factors, "primary hygiene" factors, "secondary hygiene" factors, "work environment" factors, "sense of belongingness" factors, and "growth and recognition" factors. The hypotheses formulated are summarized in Table 1.

2.3. Sampling Method, Data Collection and Analysis

Primary data were gathered using both quantitative and qualitative methods. This involved a questionnaire that included questions about retention strategies and attrition factors, along with an interview checklist. Employee responses were recorded and analysed utilizing Microsoft Excel Pivot and R.

2.4. Sample Size and Analysis of the Dataset

Sample Size

Data were collected from both current and former staff using a simple random sampling technique. A total of 32 participants, consisting of 24 current staff and 8 former staff from both technical and non-technical divisions, completed the online questionnaire. To validate the quantitative responses, two focus group discussions were organized, with each group comprising 11 respondents (both male and female). Descriptive analysis of the dataset included calculating the mean values for various variables. This approach was used to examine the mean and variance across different questions and to derive conclusions based on the staff's responses.

Questionnaire for the staff

The questionnaire comprised three main sections. The first section included questions about the socio-demographics of the staff, while the second section focused on factors influencing retention strategies. The third section contained open-ended questions. The questions in the second section were measured using a five-point Likert scale, which included:

- 1 = "Strongly Disagree (SD)",
- 2 = "Disagree (D)",
- 3 = "Neither Agree nor Disagree (NAD) ",
- 4 = "Agree (A)",
- 5 = "Strongly Agree (SA) "

2.5. Data analysis

2.5.1. Staff socio-demographic profile

The socio-demographic profile of the 32 respondents and their relationship with staff perception and behaviour about the retention strategies were analysed.

2.5.2. Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for the Retention Factors

To assess normal distribution, a Shapiro-Wilk test was performed with a threshold value of 0.05. Subsequently, the survey's significance was determined using a one-way ANOVA test, a common method for comparing multiple groups and identifying any significant differences between them.

Following the normality test, a regression analysis was conducted to establish the correlation between the factors influencing employee satisfaction towards retention (as shown in Table 1). Data from 32 respondents were collected, and the Beta Value for each predictor variable was calculated. This value, representing the standardized regression coefficient, indicates the degree of influence each predictor variable has on the criterion variable. A higher Beta Value signifies a stronger impact of the predictor variable on the criterion variable.

Additionally, descriptive statistics were employed to compare retention factors and calculate the means of the variables. In this study, descriptive statistics were used to identify the most significant factors influencing employee retention.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1. Staff socio-demographic profile

The socio-demographic profiles of staff and their relationship with staff perception and behaviour regarding retention strategies are presented in Table 2.

From Table 2, it is evident that 78% of the respondents were male, while 22% were female, indicating a higher response rate from male staff. The age range of the respondents varied between 23 and 60, with the average age being 38 years. The educational background of the respondents revealed that the majority held first-degree qualifications (41%), followed by master's degree holders (38%).

The study found that 43% of the respondents had more than 10 years of total work experience, while 41% had 2 to 4 years of experience. However, the current work experience at the SRI was more prevalent among respondents with 2 to 4 years of experience. The findings also suggest that the category of respondents with experience exceeding 10 years at the SRI constituted the second-highest proportion, at 22%. Lastly, among the 32 respondents, 75% were still staff at the SRI, while 25% had transitioned to other organizations.

3.2 Retention factors influencing the employee satisfaction

The results for retention factors influencing employee satisfaction at the SRI are presented below. The 'retention factors' encompass "motivational", "primary hygiene", "secondary hygiene", "work environment", "sense of belongingness", and "growth and recognition" factors.

'Motivational' Factors

Hypothesis: 'motivational' factors will not influence the employee satisfaction variable. The output sheet is presented in Table 3.1 to infer whether there is any significant effect of 'motivational' factors on employee satisfaction at the SRI.

Table 3.1 reveals that the p-value is greater than the α value, i.e., the null hypothesis is accepted. This indicates that 'motivational' factors do not significantly impact the level of employee satisfaction at the SRI.

Table 3.2 displays the results of the regression coefficient test, illustrating how the independent variables positively and negatively influence dependent variables. The model predicts that a 1 standard deviation increase in the independent variable leads to an increase or decrease in the dependent variable while holding all other independent variables constant.

Table 3.2 indicates that the variable with the highest and positive beta value is 'a good and healthy working environment for the employees.' This suggests that employee satisfaction levels are higher when the organization provides a good and healthy working environment. The independent variables are ranked based on their degree of influence on the dependent variable, arranged in descending order from highest to lowest: 'a good and healthy working environment for the employees,' 'opportunities resulting in promotion available in the organization,' 'a sense of job security experienced by the employees,' 'opportunities for career growth provided by the organization,' and 'remuneration provided by the organization as per industry standards.'

'Primary hygiene' Factors

Hypothesis: 'primary hygiene' factors will not influence employee satisfaction at the SRI. The output sheet is presented in Table 4.1 below to infer whether there is any significant effect of 'primary hygiene' factors on employee satisfaction at the SRI.

Table 4.1 reveals that the p-value is less than the α value, i.e., the null hypothesis is not accepted, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This means 'primary hygiene' factors significantly impact the level of employee satisfaction at the SRI.

From Table 4.2, it is found that the Beta value for 'stress reduction programs like keep fit, health care among others conducted by the organization' is the highest and positive. Hence, it can be said that employee satisfaction levels are higher at the SRI when stress reduction programs like keep fit, health care are organized for the employees.

Thus, based on the degree of influence (positive or negative) of each independent variable, the dependent variable is arranged in descending order, i.e., highest to lowest, which is 'stress reduction programs like keep fit, health care among others conducted by the organization,' 'transport facilities provided by the organization,' 'good welfare measures provided for employees,' 'fringe benefits (e.g., end-of-year party, internet, get together, family involvements),' and 'availability of the daycare facility for working mothers and guardians'.

'Secondary hygiene' Factors

Hypothesis: 'secondary hygiene' factors will not influence employee satisfaction at SRI. The output sheet is presented in Table 5.1 below to infer whether there is any significant effect of 'secondary hygiene' factors on employee satisfaction at SRI.

Table 5.1 reveals that the p-value is greater than the α value, i.e., the null hypothesis is accepted. This means 'secondary hygiene' factors do not significantly impact the level of employee satisfaction at the SRI.

The Beta value for Table 5.2 shows 'focus on mentoring programs for employees' as the highest and positive. Hence, it can be said that employee satisfaction levels are higher at the SRI when there is more focus on mentoring programs.

Thus, based on the degree of influence (positive or negative) of each independent variable, the dependent variable is arranged in descending order, i.e., highest to lowest, which is 'focus more on mentoring programs for employees,' 'organization encourages higher education for employees,' and 'additional training is provided for different domain jobs/tasks'.

'Work environment' Factors

Hypothesis: 'work environment' factors will not influence employee satisfaction at the SRI. The output sheet is presented in Table 6.1 below to infer whether there is any significant effect of 'work environment' factors on employee satisfaction at the SRI.

Table 6.1 reveals that the p-value is less than the α value, i.e., the null hypothesis is not accepted, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This means 'work environment' factors significantly impact the level of employee satisfaction at the SRI.

The highest and positive beta value from Table 6.2 indicates that 'guidance and motivation provided by the immediate supervisor' is the most influential factor for employee satisfaction at SRI.

In descending order of influence (positive or negative) of each independent variable on the dependent variable, the factors are arranged as follows: 'guidance and motivation provided by the immediate supervisor,' 'opportunities for new assignments provided by the organization,' 'open communication policy followed by the organization,' 'freedom of employees' participation in management to provide their valuable thoughts and ideas,' 'organization has a good rewards and incentive system,' 'organization focuses on teamwork and also on developing leadership skills in employees,' and 'flexibility in working hours is emphasized by the organization.'

One study conducted by PwC (2018) found that poor leadership or lack of opportunities to develop leadership skills was a significant demotivating factor for employees. The study revealed that 55% of employees who left their jobs cited poor leadership as the primary reason for leaving.

'Sense of belongingness' Factors

Hypothesis: 'sense of belongingness' factors will not influence employee satisfaction at the SRI. The output sheet is presented in Table 7.1 below to infer whether there is any significant effect of 'sense of belongingness' factors on employee satisfaction at the SRI.

Table 7.1 reveals that the p-value is less than the α value, i.e., the null hypothesis is not accepted, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This means 'sense of belongingness' factors significantly impacts the level of employee satisfaction at the SRI.

The Beta value for Table 7.2 shows 'organizational policies and culture create a positive environment' as the highest and positive. Hence, it can be said that the employee satisfaction level at the SRI is higher when policies and culture create a positive environment.

Thus, based on the degree of influence (positive or negative) of each independent variable, the dependent variable is arranged in descending order, i.e., highest to lowest, which is 'organizations' policies and culture create a positive environment,' 'respect and fair treatment received from managers and other employees,' 'promote work-life balance in the organization,' 'opportunities available to develop new skills,' and 'adequate leave and leave benefits are provided by the organization.'

The lack of career growth opportunities is another demotivating factor for employees. A study by Gallup (2021) found that 59% of employees surveyed said that opportunities to learn and grow were essential to their job satisfaction. The study revealed that employees who do not see opportunities for career growth and development tend to be less engaged and more likely to leave their jobs. Poor working conditions and a lack of work-life balance are also significant demotivating factors for employees. A study by Harvard Business Review (2018) found that employees who reported having a poor work-life balance were more likely to experience burnout and leave their jobs. Furthermore, a study by the Society for Human Resource Management (2019) found that employees who experience poor working conditions, such as noise, temperature, and lighting, tend to be less productive and have lower job satisfaction.

'Growth and recognition' Factors

Hypothesis: 'growth and recognition' factors will not influence employee satisfaction at the SRI. The output sheet is presented in Table 8.1 below to infer whether there is any significant effect of 'growth and recognition' factors on employee satisfaction at the SRI.

Table 8.1 reveals that the p-value is less than the α value, i.e., the null hypothesis is not accepted, and the alternative hypothesis is accepted. This means 'growth and recognition' factors significantly impact the level of employee satisfaction at the SRI.

From Table 8.2, it is found that the Beta value for 'good performance is very well recognized by the organization' is the highest and positive. Hence, it can be said that employees' satisfaction levels are higher at the SRI when their performance is recognized by the institution.

Thus, based on the degree of influence (positive or negative) of each independent variable on the dependent variable, they are arranged in descending order, i.e., highest to lowest, which is 'performance appraisal system followed is as per industry standards,' 'supervisors are approachable and cooperative in nature,' and 'the organization provides adequate training and development programs for growth'.

3.3 Socio-demographic factors that influence employee satisfaction at the SRI

From Table 9, it is evident that 80% of male respondents are either satisfied or very satisfied with the retention factors implemented by the SRI, while for the female population, this figure is slightly lower at 71%.

This indicates higher satisfaction among male employees with the organization's retention strategies. The higher satisfaction levels among male employees compared to female employees highlight a potential gender disparity in how retention factors are perceived. However, a relatively larger percentage of the female population (14%) express dissatisfaction with these strategies compared to their male counterparts (8%). Notably, almost all Principal Technologists express satisfaction with the SRI's retention factors. In contrast, 50% of Senior Research Scientists, 22% of Principal Research Scientists, and 17% of Research Scientists neither express dissatisfaction nor satisfaction with the SRI's retention strategies.

Employees with cumulative work experience exceeding 10 years constitute a relatively larger percentage (14%) compared to those with cumulative work experience between 1 to 4 years. Similarly, employees with a tenure at SRI exceeding 10 years constitute a relatively larger percentage (14%) compared to those with tenure between 1 to 4 years. However, the majority of employees with a tenure at SRI between 4 to 6 years (33%) express neither dissatisfaction nor satisfaction with the organization's retention strategies.

In Table 10, a comparison between the six retention factors and demographic variables is presented. Concerning gender, male employees exhibit higher satisfaction, considering 'primary hygiene' factors, 'secondary hygiene' factors, 'work environment', 'growth and recognition' factors, and a 'sense of belongingness' as the most influential factors compared to others. Principal Technologists demonstrate higher satisfaction compared to other roles, emphasizing 'secondary hygiene' factors as more influential. Principal Research Scientists derive satisfaction from 'motivational' factors, 'secondary hygiene' factors, 'growth and recognition' factors, and a 'sense of belongingness'.

Employees with cumulative work experience above 10 years express satisfaction with 'motivational' factors, 'primary hygiene' factors, and a 'sense of belongingness' as more influential. Conversely, employees with a tenure between 6 and 10 years derive satisfaction from all six retention factors: 'motivational' factors, 'primary hygiene' factors, 'secondary hygiene' factors, 'work environment', 'growth and recognition', and a 'sense of belongingness'. A study by KPMG (2019) found that 70% of employees who left their jobs cited inadequate compensation as the primary reason for leaving. Furthermore, a study by Towers Watson (2014) revealed that employees who are not adequately compensated tend to be less motivated, have lower job satisfaction, and are more likely to leave their jobs.

3.4 Present and past employee perspectives towards the retention of employees at the SRI

This section responds to current and former employees on demotivating factors (Table 11). Current and former employees have cited several demotivating factors that negatively impact their job satisfaction and retention. These factors include poor leadership, lack of career growth opportunities, inadequate compensation, poor working conditions, and a lack of work-life balance.

3.5. Implications of the retention factors on employee satisfaction at a State Research Institute

The study suggests a need for the SRI to reevaluate its approach to 'motivational' factors, with a specific focus on cultivating a positive and healthy working environment. Enhancing workplace well-being could substantially elevate employee satisfaction. Stress reduction programs, encompassing initiatives like keep-fit activities and health care, emerge as critical elements for fostering a healthier and more content workforce. The implementation and promotion of such programs hold the potential to significantly contribute to employee satisfaction.

While the study did not find significant impacts of 'secondary hygiene' factors, the emphasis on mentoring programs stands out as noteworthy. Strengthening mentoring initiatives within the organization could notably enhance employee satisfaction, particularly in terms of providing support for career growth and skill development.

Furthermore, 'work environment' factors, particularly the guidance and motivation provided by immediate supervisors, are identified as key influencers. Enhancing leadership skills and ensuring that supervisors actively contribute to a positive 'work environment' may lead to higher levels of employee satisfaction.

The positive impact of organizational policies and culture on employee satisfaction is evident. Fostering a positive and inclusive culture, promoting work-life balance, and ensuring fair treatment are crucial for enhancing the 'sense of belongingness' among employees.

Additionally, recognizing good performance emerges as a pivotal factor in employee satisfaction. Implementing a robust performance appraisal system, ensuring approachable supervisors, and providing training and development opportunities can contribute to a more satisfied workforce.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

The study identifies 'primary hygiene', 'work environment', 'sense of belongingness', and 'growth and recognition' factors as key elements influencing employee satisfaction at the State Research Institutes (SRI). Specific factors affecting satisfaction include stress reduction programs, guidance from immediate supervisors, positive organizational policies and culture, and recognition of good performance.

Socio-demographic factors, such as gender, role as a principal technologist, 4-6 years of work experience, and 6-10 years of employment at the SRI, impact employee satisfaction. Retention measures at the SRI have also influenced the socio-demographic profile of employees, with distinct motivations observed for different groups.

The study recommends targeted policies and interventions for SRIs, including specialized training for supervisors, initiatives to improve work-life balance, and strategies to enhance organizational culture. Recognizing and appreciating employee performance through established programs is highlighted as a means to boost morale and improve satisfaction. These recommendations aim to contribute to enhanced retention rates at SRIs.

The study emphasizes the dynamic nature of employee satisfaction factors and suggests implementing regular surveys and feedback mechanisms to stay attuned to evolving employee needs. Proactive measures, such as these, are seen as essential for continuous improvement in the development and adjustment of retention strategies over time.

Funding

This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Declaration of conflicting interests

The Authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

Research data

The data for this research is available upon reasonable requests.

REFERENCES

1. Al-Abbadi, L. H. (2021). The effect of sustainable HRM practices on employee job outcomes of service industry in Jordan. *Journal of Management Information and Decision Sciences*. Volume 24, Special Issue 6.
2. Allen, D. G., Bryant, P. C., and Vardaman, J. M. (2010). Retaining talent: Replacing misconceptions with evidence-based strategies. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 24(2), 48-64.
3. Arokiasamy, A. R. A. (2013). A qualitative study on causes and effects of employee turnover in the private sector in Malaysia. *Middle East Journal of Scientific Research*, 16(11), 1532-1541.
4. Chukwuka, E. J., and Nwakoby, N. P. (2018). Effect of human resource management practices on employee retention and performance in Nigerian insurance industry. *World Journal of Research and Review*, 6(4), 262667.
5. Elsafty, A., and Oraby, M. (2022). The Impact of Training on Employee Retention: An Empirical Research on the Private Sector in Egypt. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 17(5), 58-74.
6. Ewool, E. M., Azinga, S. A., and Kamil, N. M. (2021). The Influence of Employee Recognition on Employee Engagement: The Moderating Role of Salary Satisfaction. *International Journal of Academic Research in Accounting, Finance and Management Science*, 11(3), 433-456.
7. Gallup (2021). What employees want most. Retrieved from <https://www.gallup.com/workplace/285674/employees-want.aspx>
8. Harvard Business Review (2018). Burnout is about your workplace, not your people. Retrieved from <https://hbr.org/2018/06/burnout-is-about-your-workplace-not-your-people>
9. Jayasekara, W. A. S. S., and Weerasinghe, T. D. (2018). The Nexus between Employee Motivation and Turnover Intention: Moderating Role of Generation Gap (With Special Reference to the Executives of a Leading PVC Manufacturing Firm in Sri Lanka). *Kelaniya Journal of Human Resource Management*, 13(2).
10. Korantwi-Barimah, J. S. (2017). Factors influencing the Retention of Academic staff in a Ghanaian technical University. *Human Resource Management Research*, 7(3), 111-119.
11. KPMG (2019). Why do employees leave their jobs? Retrieved from <https://home.kpmg/xx/en/home/insights/2019/05/why-do-employees-leave-their-jobs.html>
12. Mugo, C. N., Muyia, H. M., Ongus, J. R., and K'Obonyo, P. O. (2018b). The influence of remuneration on staff retention in a research institution in Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 9(3), 120-130.
13. Mugo, W. M., Kibet, L. K., and Waiganjo, E. W. (2018a). Influence of financial and non-financial incentives on employee retention in selected non-governmental organizations in Kenya. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 13(2), 1-12.

14. PwC. (2018). 2018 PwC employee financial wellness survey. Retrieved from <https://www.pwc.com/us/en/private-company-services/publications/assets/pwc-2018-employee-financial-wellness-survey.pdf>
15. Rawashdeh, A. M., and Tamimi, S. A. (2020). The impact of employee perceptions of training on organizational commitment and turnover intention: An empirical study of nurses in Jordanian hospitals. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 44(2/3), 191-207.
16. Saleem, S., and Amin, S. (2013). The impact of organizational support for career development and supervisory support on employee performance: An empirical study from Pakistani academic sector. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 5(5), 194-207.
17. Shafiuddin, M., and Al Nassibi, M. G. M. M. (2022). Impact Of ‘work environment’ on Job Satisfaction and Employee Retention: An Empirical Study from Private Sector Banks In Hyderabad Of Telangana State In India. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(9), 2467-2483.
18. Shakeel, N., and But, S. (2015). Factors influencing employee retention: An integrated perspective. *Journal of Resources Development and Management*, 6(1), 32-49.
19. Singh, D. (2019). A literature review on employee retention with a focus on recent trends. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science and Technology*, 6(1), 425-431.
20. Society for Human Resource Management (2019). SHRM job satisfaction and engagement: The road to economic recovery. Retrieved from <https://www.shrm.org/hr-today/trends-and-forecasting/research-and-surveys/Documents/2019-Employee-Job-Satisfaction-and-Engagement-Report.pdf>
21. Son, S., and Kim, D. Y. (2021). Organizational career growth and career commitment: Moderated mediation model of work engagement and role modelling. *The International Journal of Human Resource Management*, 32(20), 4287-4310.
22. Tadesse, W. M. (2018). Factors affecting employee retention in Ethiopian public organizations. *Journal of Strategic Human Resource Management*, 7(3), 22-32.
23. Towers Watson (2014). The 2014 Towers Watson global workforce study. Retrieved from <https://www.towerswatson.com/-/media/towers-watson/assets/2014/07/2014-towers-Watson-global-workforce-study-report-emea.pdf>

Appendices

Table 1: Hypotheses tested based on staff retention factors.

Retention factors	Hypotheses formulated
‘motivational’ factors	H01: Opportunities for career growth provided by the organization do not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H02: Retention of employees does not get significantly influenced by the remuneration provided by the organization if it’s as per industry standards
	H03: Retention of staff does not get significantly influenced if opportunities resulting in the promotion are available in the organization
	H04: Retention of staff does not get significantly influenced if a sense of job security is experienced by the staff
	H05: A good and healthy working environment does not significantly influence the retention of staff
‘primary hygiene’ factors	H01: Transport facilities provided by the organization do not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H02: Availability of daycare facility for working mothers and guardians does not significantly influence retention of staff
	H03: Good welfare measures provided for the staff do not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H04: Organization providing fringe benefits does not significantly influence retention of staff
	H05: Stress reduction programs like yoga, meditation, health care, etc. conducted by the organization do not significantly influence the retention of staff

'secondary hygiene' factors	H01: Additional training provided for different domain jobs or tasks does not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H02: Organization encouraging higher education does not significantly influence retention of staff
	H03: Mentoring programs for staff do not significantly influence the retention of staff
'work environment' factors	H01: Flexibility in working hours emphasized by the organization does not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H02: A good reward and incentive system do not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H03: Focus on teamwork and developing leadership skills in the staff does not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H04: Guidance and motivation provided by the immediate supervisor do not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H05: Opportunities for new assignments provided by the organization do not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H06: Open communication policy followed by the organization does not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H07: Feedback provided by the superiors for every small work done does not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H08: Freedom of employee's participation in management does not significantly influence retention of staff
'sense of belongingness' factors	H01: Respect and fair treatment received from managers and other staff does not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H02: Opportunities available to develop new skills do not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H03: Adequate leave and leave benefits provided by the organization do not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H04: Organizational policies and culture which create a positive environment do not significantly influence the retention of staff
	H05: Promoting Work-life Balance by the organization does not significantly influence the Retention of staff
'growth and recognition' factors	H01: Performance appraisal system followed as per industry standards does not significantly influence retention of staff
	H02: Recognition of good performance does not significantly influence retention of staff
	H03: Approachable and cooperative supervisor does not significantly influence Retention of staff
	H04: Adequate training and development programs provided by the organization for growth do not significantly influence the retention of staff

Table 2: Socio-demographic profile of staff

Characteristic	Profile	Frequency (%)
Gender	Male	25 (78)
	Female	7 (22)
Age	Mean	38
	Minimum	23
	Maximum	60
Education qualification	Diploma	1 (3)
	First degree	13 (41)
	Masters	12 (38)
	PhD	6 (19)

Division	Administration	4 (13)
	Commercialization	3 (9)
	Directorate	2 (6)
	Finance	2 (6)
	Genetic conservation	9 (28)
	Genetic diversity	9 (28)
	Plant Protection	3 (9)
Total Work Experience	2 – 4 years	13 (41)
	4 – 6 years	1 (3)
	6 – 10 years	4 (13)
	Above 10 years	14 (43)
Experience with Current Organization	2 – 4 years	21 (66)
	4 – 6 years	3 (9)
	6 – 10 years	1 (3)
	Above 10 years	7 (22)
Currently a staff of SRI	Yes	24 (75)
	No	8 (25)

Source: Primary data

Table 3.1 ANOVA Output of ‘motivational’ Factors

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	6.742	8	0.843	1.131	0.380
Residual	17.133	23	0.745		
Total	23.875	31			

Source: primary data

Table 3.2 Standardized Regression Coefficients for Motivation Factors

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients B	Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta
1	(Constant)	1.175	0.861	
	Opportunities for career growth provided by the organization	-0.149	0.190	-0.159
	Remuneration provided by the organization should be as per industry standards	-0.128	0.126	-0.163
	Opportunities resulting in the promotion are available in the organization	0.395	0.255	0.338
	A sense of job security should be experienced by the employees	-0.031	0.174	-0.029
	A good and healthy working environment for the employees	0.358	0.137	0.484
	a. Dependent Variable: employee satisfaction			

Source: primary data

Table 4.1 ANOVA output of ‘primary hygiene’ factors

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	15.792	14	1.128	2.372	0.047
Residual	8.083	17	.475		
Total	23.875	31			

Source: primary data

Table 4.2 Standardized Regression Coefficients for ‘primary hygiene’ factors

Model		Unstandardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta
2	(Constant)	1.318	0.518	
	Transport facility provided by the organization.	0.289	0.102	0.432
	Availability of day care facility for working mothers and guardians.	-0.160	0.127	-0.249
	Good welfare measures are provided for the employees.	0.066	0.153	0.093
	Fringe benefits (e.g., end-of-year party, internet, get-together, family involvement etc.)	-0.022	0.176	-0.026
	Stress reduction programs like keeping fit, health care etc. Conducted by the organization	0.326	0.121	0.500
a. Dependent Variable: employee satisfaction				

Source: primary data

Table 5.1 ANOVA output of ‘secondary hygiene’ factors

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	8.658	8	1.082	1.636	0.169
Residual	15.217	23	0.662		
Total	23.875	31			

Source: primary data

Table 5.2 Standardized Regression Coefficients for ‘secondary hygiene’ factors

Model		Unstandardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta
3	(Constant)	1.149	1.201	
	Organization encourages higher education for employees.	0.098	0.260	0.063
	Additional training is provided for different domain jobs/task	-0.004	0.169	-0.005
	Focus more on mentoring programs for employees.	0.409	0.190	0.480
a. Dependent Variable: employee satisfaction				

Source: primary data

Table 6.1 ANOVA output of ‘work environment’ factors

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	16.875	15	1.125	2.571	0.035

Residual	7.000	16	0.438		
Total	23.875	31			

Source: primary data

Table 6.2 Standardized Regression Coefficients for ‘work environment’ factors

Model		Unstandardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta
4	(Constant)	0.604	0.846	
	An open communication policy is followed by the organization	0.101	0.225	0.089
	Flexibility in working hours is emphasized by the organization.	-0.092	0.151	-0.123
	Organization has a good rewards and incentive system	-0.017	0.194	-0.021
	Organization focuses on teamwork and developing leadership skills in the employees.	-0.044	0.211	-0.052
	Guidance and motivation provided by the immediate supervisor	0.277	0.217	0.358
	Opportunities for new assignments provided by the organization.	0.335	0.238	0.338
	Freedom of employees’ participation in management to provide their valuable thoughts and ideas.	0.053	0.157	0.076
a. Dependent Variable: employee satisfaction				

Source: primary data

Table 7.1 ANOVA output of ‘sense of belongingness’ factors

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	13.194	10	1.319	2.594	0.032
Residual	10.681	21	0.509		
Total	23.875	31			

Source: primary data

Table 7.2 Standardized Regression Coefficients for ‘sense of belongingness’ factors

Model		Unstandardized B	Coefficients Std. Error	Standardized Coefficients Beta
5	(Constant)	1.514	0.713	
	Respect and fair treatment received from managers and other employees.	0.257	0.157	0.319
	Adequate leave and leave benefits are provided by the organization	-0.187	0.150	-0.203
	Opportunities available to develop new skills	-0.059	0.151	-0.075

Organizational policies and culture create a positive environment	0.288	0.153	0.380
Promote work-life balance in the organization	0.096	0.198	0.114
a. Dependent Variable: employee satisfaction			

Source: primary data

Table 8.1 ANOVA output of ‘growth and recognition’ factors

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	15.408	11	1.401	3.309	0.010
Residual	8.467	20	.423		
Total	23.875	31			

Source: primary data

Table 8.2 Standardized Regression Coefficients for ‘growth and recognition’ factors

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients
		B	Std. Error	Beta
6	(Constant)	0.934	0.628	
	Performance appraisal systems followed as per industry standards	0.115	0.166	0.130
	Good performance is very well recognized by the organization	0.472	0.167	0.607
	Supervisors are approachable and cooperative	0.049	0.166	0.053
	The organization provides adequate training and development programs for growth	-0.101	0.146	-0.120
a. Dependent Variable: employee satisfaction				

Source: primary data

Table 9 Impact of Socio-demographic Factors on the Level of employee satisfaction

	Very Satisfied	Satisfied	Neither Dissatisfied nor Satisfied	Dissatisfied
Gender				
Male	28%	52%	12%	8%
Female	14%	57%	14%	14%
Role/Designation				
Principal Research Scientist	22%	44%	22%	11%
Research Scientist	17%	50%	17%	17%
Senior Research Scientist	0%	50%	50%	0%
Technician	20%	70%	0%	10%
Principal Technologies	60%	40%	0%	0%
Cumulative work experience				
1 - 4 years				
4 - 6 years	38%	54%	0%	8%
6 - 10 years	0%	100%	0%	0%
Above 10	25%	50%	25%	0%
	14%	50%	21%	14%
Length of work at SRI				
1 - 4 years				
4 - 6 years	33%	48%	10%	10%
6 - 10 years	0%	67%	33%	0%
Above 10	100%	0%	0%	0%

	0%	71%	14%	14%
--	----	-----	-----	-----

Source: primary data

Table 10 Descriptive statistic output of the socio-demographic profile and identified retention factors

	'motivational' factors	'primary hygiene' factors	'secondary hygiene' factors	'work environment'	'growth and recognition'
Gender					
Female	3.94	2.51	3.67	3.33	3.68
Male	3.82	3.09	3.72	3.55	3.75
Role/Designation					
Principal Research Scientists	4.20	3.40	4.00	3.57	4.00
Principal technologist	3.82	2.71	3.69	3.71	3.96
Research scientists	3.77	3.17	3.94	3.36	3.54
Senior Research Scientists	3.80	3.40	3.50	3.07	3.50
Technician	3.88	3.00	3.63	3.41	3.65
Cumulative work experience					
1 - 4 years	3.82	2.88	3.79	3.58	3.88
4 - 6 years	3.40	1.60	2.67	2.71	3.00
6 - 10 years	3.70	2.80	3.75	3.46	3.56
Above 10	3.96	3.19	3.69	3.49	3.70
Length of work at SRI					
1 - 4 years	3.87	3.07	3.86	3.67	3.83
4 - 6 years	3.33	1.73	3.11	2.67	3.17
6 - 10 years	4.20	4.00	4.67	3.71	4.50
Above 10	3.97	3.03	3.38	3.31	3.57

Source: primary data

Table 11: Demotivating factors by current and former employees

Current staff	Former staff
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Compensation issues related to technologist premiums • High deductions for benefits (superannuation, provident fund) • Low labor force appreciation, especially in fieldwork • Lack of overtime for all staff • No rotation of headship roles • Unavailability of necessary tools and field attire • No health facilities for workers and families • Discouraging supervisory behavior • Lack of internet access and favoritism • Gossip and unnecessary negativity • Vertical hierarchical communication issues 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor ‘work environment’ • Lack of teamwork • Lack of recognition of organizational structure • Insufficient funding • Outdated laboratory facilities • Staff disunity